

THE IMPORTANCE OF LEGAL LITERACY IN SPIRITUAL AND MORAL EDUCATION OF WOMEN

Mamatova Mavluda Toirovna

3rd stage student of the course

"History, Basics of Additional State Law"

Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

Abstract. This article discusses the issues of raising the status of women, increasing their activity in state and society management, education, health care, science and other fields, and increasing their legal literacy. In addition, it will be discussed about the work being done to ensure their equality in socio-cultural, political and gender issues.

Key words: Women and girls, social-cultural, political-legal, gender equality, law, spirituality, education.

INTRODUCTION

Women of Uzbekistan are actively participating in the life of the state and society, their position in the family is being strengthened. The socially oriented policy carried out by the head of our state creates the necessary opportunities for our women to live a truly happy life, to ensure their rights and freedoms, to develop intellectually and spiritually, and to fulfill their professional and family obligations in a harmonious manner.

Under the leadership of the Honorable President Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoev, special attention is paid to increasing the socio-political activity of women and girls, protecting their health, supporting their aspirations and initiatives, and creating decent working and living conditions for them.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Philosophers, historians, and even legal scholars have studied this issue for a reason: the main link of society is the family, and today it is important to raise the spiritual world of women, especially young people, to educate them in the spirit of national and universal values. The issue of education has become one of the most urgent issues in the focus of attention of all countries and scientists in the era of globalization.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

In accordance with the Family Code, husband and wife enjoy equal rights and have equal obligations in the family, each of the husband and wife is free to choose the type of occupation, occupation, and place of residence.

According to Article 26 of this Code, personal items other than valuables and jewelry (clothes, shoes, etc.), even though they were taken at the expense of the common funds of the husband and wife during the marriage, were used by them. is the private property of husband and wife.

Violence is the intentional physical, mental, sexual or economic influence of one person on another person, or the threat of using measures to influence such influence on his life, health, sexual integrity, an illegal action (inaction) that violates their honor, dignity and other rights and freedoms protected by law.

Domestic violence is defined as the act (inaction) of violence against other members of the family (wife, parents, children, etc.). In general, according to statistical data, women suffer from domestic violence in most cases. Domestic violence can take the form of sexual, physical, economic and psychological violence.

Adoption of laws serves to create an environment of intolerance of oppression and violence against women in society, to ensure protection of women's rights, freedoms and legal interests from oppression and violence, to raise legal awareness and legal culture in society.

It is known that in the 21st century, humanity has entered the era of globalization of world processes, the era in which the values of human subjectivity and active life position and the right to self-realization are promoted. One of the aspects characteristic of the times is the need for full and equal participation of women in all spheres of life within the framework of the formation of democratic states and raising the level of citizenship of the society.

In particular, the reforms in Uzbekistan have significantly increased the social role of women. The principle of equal rights and equal opportunities for men and women, which is enshrined in Article 46 of the Constitution and reflected in many laws, is relevant in the Republic of Uzbekistan. In this regard, international standards of human rights and fundamental freedoms are being followed within the framework of the implementation of the Beijing Declaration and the platform for action for equality between men and women.

In the current era, attention is being paid to the leadership role of women and the image of a politician. Therefore, it is appropriate to study the image of a female politician in a separate category. The issues of forming the political image of a

woman, which determines her place and position in society, and her behavior in public, as well as the wide promotion of her program and purpose, are also relevant. Uzbekistan is conscientiously trying to fulfill its international obligations regarding women's issues. Our country, as a member of the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination of Women's Rights, pays special attention to the issue of harmonizing its norms with the national legislation. In particular, important steps have been taken in this regard in our country.

Women can participate in the election process as voters, candidates for deputies, members of the election commission, observers, authorized representatives of the party, trustees, equally and freely, openly and transparently. "Guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men in the exercise of electoral rights" were strengthened in a separate chapter in the Law "On Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men". Based on it, women and men have equal rights to elect and be elected to representative bodies of power. Political parties provide equal rights and opportunities for women and men when nominating candidates for the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the local Councils of People's Deputies.

CONCLUSION

Honoring a woman and showing respect to her is one of the noble characteristics of the Uzbek people. In this sense, historical works of national importance are being carried out in Uzbekistan to strengthen the place and status of women in society. The stability and development of the political, socio-spiritual environment in society is related to the attitude and attention to women, youth, and family. In our republic, issues related to women are in the center of attention of the state and society. Our opinion is evidenced by the fact that the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that "Women - girls and men have equal rights" and that this is followed in all aspects of life.

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